

Molecular Complexes between Chloranil and Benzoic Acids in different Solvents and Application of the Hammett Equation

K. K. MAJUMDAR^a and S. C. LAHIRI^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, F. C. College, Diamond Harbour-743 311

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Kalyani University, Kalyani-741 235

Manuscript received 20 December 1993, revised 22 July 1994, accepted 27 July 1994

Stability constants for the molecular complexes of chloranil with benzoic acid and substituted benzoic acids in aliphatic hydrogen bonded solvent CHCl_3 and aromatic aprotic solvent C_6H_6 have been determined. The stability constants of the substituted benzoic acid complexes have been found to be greater in CHCl_3 compared to those in C_6H_6 though the reverse has been found to be true for benzoic acid complex. The changes in the stability constant with solvents can not be properly interpreted but it is likely that dispersion forces are mainly responsible for the changes in the stability constant with solvent systems.

Correlation of the stability constants in terms of the Hammett equation has been found to be poor but the reaction solvent parameter (ρ) has been found to be positive and negative respectively for CHCl_3 and C_6H_6 , indicating that the aliphatic hydrogen bonded solvent and aromatic aprotic solvent act in a different way.

Quinones are well known for bacteriostatic, antifungal and antitumour activities¹. They are also characterised by their marked capability to form charge transfer (CT) or molecular complexes and their high chemical reactivities². The substituted chloro derivative, chloranil is also a good electron acceptor². Studies on the CT complexes of quinones with various compounds are reported² but reactions of quinones with aromatic acids like benzoic acid, a well-known antifungal compound, have not been reported.

The purpose of the present work is to find whether chloranil and benzoic acid (and its derivatives) form complexes in solution and the results are given.

Results and Discussion

The equilibrium constant for the complex between D and A.

[where A is chloranil and D is benzoic acid or substituted acids] can be written as

$$K_C = \frac{[\text{AD}]}{[\text{A}][\text{D}]} \frac{\gamma_{\text{AD}}}{\gamma_{\text{A}}\gamma_{\text{D}}} \quad (2)$$

The activity coefficients of A and D can be calculated from their solubility parameters or vapour pressure measurement but the method is difficult and rarely used. γ_{AD} is very difficult to determine^{2,3}. Since most of the compounds are non-electrolytes, it is the usual practice to consider $\gamma_{\text{AD}}/\gamma_{\text{A}}\gamma_{\text{D}}$ to be unity for dilute solutions. In our works, the concentrations of A and D in solution range between 1.8×10^{-3} to $4.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ so that the activity quotient can be reasonably assumed to be unity in all cases.

The usual expressions for the calculation of equilibrium constants like Benesi-Hildebrand, Scott or Rose-Drago^{2,3} had been avoided but we utilised an iterative method which imposed no restrictions regarding the concentrations of A and D. Let C_1 and C_2 be the initial concentrations of A^{d} and D and x be the concentration of complex at equilibrium we have

$$d_1 = \epsilon_1 C_1 l \text{ (for chloranil)} \quad (3)$$

$$d_2 = \epsilon_1 (C_1 - x) l + \epsilon_2 x l \quad (4)$$

where ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are the molar absorptivities of chloranil and the complex respectively, so that

$$d_2 - d_1 = (\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1) x l$$

$$x = \frac{d_2 - d_1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1) l} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{and } K = \frac{x}{(C_1 - x)(C_2 - x)} = \frac{d_2 - d_1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1) l (C_1 - x)(C_2 - x)} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{or } C_1 - x = \frac{d_2 - d_1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)(C_2 - x)K} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{C_1}{d_2 - d_1} = \frac{l}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1) l} + \frac{1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)(C_2 - x) l K} \quad (l = 1 \text{ cm}) \quad (8)$$

since x is likely to be small, we plotted $C_1/(d_2 - d_1)$ against $1/C_2$ from which approximate values of $1/(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)$ and x were determined. The values of x were utilised to get refined values of K , $1/(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)$ and x . The iteration has been repeated till constant

values of $1/(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)$ and K are obtained. Usually two to three iterations are required to get the constant values. The molar absorptivity values of the complexes and the equilibrium constants are given in Table 1.

Solute-solvent interaction is an universal phenomenon and is always associated with solvation process though interaction may be strong or weak. Moreover, the solvents always compete with either donor or acceptor or both to form (AS) or (DS) type of complexes. It is known that chloranil forms CT complex with benzene or chloroform in heptane and the equilibrium constant of (AD) complex can thus be obtained from the relation,

$$K_{c(\text{corr})}^{\text{AD}} = K_{c(\text{obs})}^{\text{AD}} [1 + K^{\text{AS}}(\text{S})] [1 + K^{\text{DS}}(\text{S})] \quad (9)$$

But benzoic acids do not absorb in the visible region in C_6H_6 or in CHCl_3 and the possibility of the complex formation of benzoic acids with solvent may be possible but unknown. However, the effect of complex formation of chloranil with solvents can be considered to be eliminated as the blank solutions contain C_6H_6 + chloranil or CHCl_3 + chloranil (d_1) and the effect has been taken into consideration in the calculation.

It is not possible to ascribe the nature of the interactions in the formation of the complexes. The complexes are fairly stable and it is expected that both specific, i.e. chemical interaction (like charge

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	Substituted benzoic acid (BA)	$K_{\text{AD}} (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1})$		$-\Delta G^\circ (\text{KJ mol}^{-1})$		$\epsilon_{\text{AD}} \times 10^2 (\text{m}^2 \text{mol}^{-1})$		ρ_{Hammett}	
		in CHCl_3	in C_6H_6	in CHCl_3	in C_6H_6	in CHCl_3	in C_6H_6	in CHCl_3	in C_6H_6
1.	Benzoic acid	119.5 (335.6)	230.6 (1975.5)	11.85	13.48	69.2	24.54	-	-
2.	3-Chloro BA	125.0 (351.0)	71.6 (613.4)	11.96	10.58	69.2	47.54	+0.05	-1.37
3.	3-Bromo BA	156.3 (438.9)	125.0 (1070.9)	12.52	11.96	69.2	42.54	+0.30	-0.68
4.	3-Iodo BA	250.0 (702.1)	153.9 (1318.5)	13.68	12.48	69.2	32.54	+0.92	-0.50
5.	4-Chloro BA	166.67 (468.0)	134.6 (1153.1)	12.68	12.15	69.2	93.97	+0.63	-1.02
6.	4-Bromo BA	227.3 (638.3)	185.2 (1586.6)	13.45	12.94	69.2	32.54	+1.21	-0.41
7.	4-Iodo BA	234.4 (658.2)	208.3 (1784.5)	13.52	13.23	402.5	32.54	+1.04	-0.16

transfer, hydrogen bonding) and non-specific, i.e. physical interactions (like dispersion interactions *etc.*) are involved in the formation of the complexes. The solvent effect on the equilibrium constants of the complexes are apparent from the Table 1. The apparently corrected equilibrium constants² using K_c of chloranil + benzene and chloranil + CHCl_3 complexes⁴ in *n*-heptane using equation (9) is given in the parenthesis, though the correction is not necessary in the present cases.

The complexes of benzoic acids with chloranil have been found to have high K values not observed in case of complexes of chloranil with π -donors like benzene. However, the possibility of π - π -CT complexes is reinforced by the formation of strong H-bonding,

i.e. the complexes may be stabilised by strong H-bonding. The shift towards the blue indicates the possibility of H-bonding capability of benzoic acids with chloranil. This leads to a substantially high value $-\Delta G^\circ$ of the complexes. Though it is not possible to predict the ΔH° values but thermodynamically H-bonding of the type shown above should lead to a decrease in entropy, i.e. $-T\Delta S^\circ$ is positive or ΔH should be slightly more negative than those of ΔG° values and probably close to ΔH° values of H-bonded complexes.

The molar absorption coefficients (Table 1) of the complexes in benzene are always appreciably greater than those in chloroform in spite of the fact that the values obtained from the intercepts are likely to be less accurate. The reason for the anomalous behaviour of molar absorption coefficients in benzene and chloroform stems out from the fact that benzoic acid and substituted benzoic acids probably exist as an equilibrium mixtures of monomers and dimers, dimers being more predominant in aprotic solvent benzene than in hydrogen bonded chloroform.

The equilibrium constants for the complexes for substituted benzoic acids are greater in CHCl_3 than those in C_6H_6 but the reverse is true for benzoic acid. It is seen that K values increase systematically from chloro- to iodo-substituted acids in both the solvents but the values for *meta*-substituted acids are considerably lower than those for *para*-substituted acids and the results may be related to less electron-withdrawing capabilities of the *para*-substituted halogens compared to those of *meta*-substituted ones.

Furthermore, the greater stability of the complexes in CHCl_3 compared to that in C_6H_6 can be attributed to greater stabilisation of the ground state compared to that of the excited state with the increase in the relative polarity of the solvent defined by Dimroth's E_T values^{5,6} (39.1 for CHCl_3 compared to 34.5 for C_6H_6).

Understanding the solvent effect requires the consideration of the solvation cycle^{3,7} for the transfer of reaction from the gas phase (g) to solution (s),

$\Delta E_{\text{D}, \text{ solv}}$ *etc.* consist of two parts : (i) $\Delta E_{\text{D}, \text{ CH}}$ energy due to the formation of the complex arising from specific or chemical interactions and (ii) $\Delta E_{\text{D}, \text{ PH}}$ energy due to physical interactions (non-specific) due to complex formation with solvent. The gas phase values are not known but must be different from the condensed phase and in the process of solvation of the uncharged species, specific chemical interactions can be assumed to be small and negligible, the main contribution to the solvation process arises from non-specific interactions. The cycle may be represented as

The non-specific solvation energy is known to consist of two parts⁷, i.e. energy of dispersion in-

$$\text{and } \Delta E_s = \Delta E_g + [\Delta E_{\text{DA}(\text{PH})} - \Delta E_{\text{D}, \text{ PH}} - \Delta E_{\text{A}, \text{ PH}}]$$

teractions (ΔE^d) and energy of electrostatic interactions. Thus, the difference in energy of the complexes in two solvents arises mainly from the difference in the non-specific solvation parts of the complexes and the reactants. For a particular complex or particular group of complexes, the electrostatic part can be assumed to be approximately the same, the difference in the values of the two solvents should arise from the dispersion interaction. However, the exact calculations are difficult and have yet not been proved successful.

It is interesting to examine the possibility of correlating the equilibrium constants with substituents using the Hammett equation⁸ with known values of the substituent constant (σ). The relationship is

$$\log \frac{(K_{AD})_{\text{subs}}}{(K_{AD})_{\text{ref}}} = \rho \sigma$$

The correlation have been found to be poor (Table 1), particularly for 3-chloro and 3-bromo compounds in CHCl_3 but for 4-bromo and 4-iodo compounds in C_6H_6 , the ρ -values have been found to be positive and negative for CHCl_3 and C_6H_6 respectively, i.e. the behaviour of the substituents are exactly opposite in these solvents. Usually positive ρ means the development of negative charge at the reaction centre on proceeding towards equilibrium and vice versa^{6,7,9}. It is likely that the hydrogen bonded aliphatic solvent CHCl_3 and aprotic aromatic solvent C_6H_6 behave in a different way. It is to be noted that the substituent constants are considered to be the same in all solvent systems which appear to be gross over-simplification¹⁰.

σ is a measure of overall polar effect exerted by the substituent on the reaction and consists of two parts : inductive effect (electron-withdrawing or electron-donating group) and field effect operating through the medium. Obviously, the field effect is very much dependent on solvent. Moreover, both mesomeric effect and field effect should change in the excited state and in CT complexes, the excited state being more important; naturally σ -values should change. However, we are unable to assign proper reasons for the change ρ or σ values.

Experimental

Chloranil, benzoic acid (both AnalaR) and chloro-, bromo- and iodo-substituted benzoic acids (Puriss, Fluka) were used as such. Benzene and chloroform (spectroscopic quality; Sisco) were distilled before use.

Benzoic acids and chloranil are known to absorb strongly in the uv region, the absorptions being somewhat dependent on the solvents. The complex formation between chloranil and benzoic acids are marked by the characteristic changes in the absorbance values as well as the changes in absorption maxima in the uv and visible region. However, since all the species absorb strongly in the uv region, the actual determination of the stability constants of the complexes may be difficult from studies in the uv region. Therefore, we preferred to use the absorption of chloranil in the region 370–400 nm where benzoic acids do not absorb. The complex formation between chloranil and benzoic acids was

Fig. 1. Plots of absorbance vs λ : (O) chloranil in CHCl_3 and (D) chloranil + benzoic acid in CHCl_3 ; [Chloranil] = 2.0×10^{-3} M, [Benzoic acid] = 2.0×10^{-3} M.

characterised by the shift in the absorption maximum of chloranil (373 and 530 nm) towards the shorter region (371 and 525 nm) (Fig. 1). Moreover, there was an appreciable changes in the absorption values in chloranil.

No attempt had been made to determine the composition of the complex and the complexes were assumed to be 1 : 1 in nature. For the determination of the stability constants of the complexes, chloranil and benzoic acids were mixed in varying proportion in a particular solvent. The absorptivity values of the mixtures and the suitable blanks containing chloranil only were noted. Measurements were made with a Varian 630 spectrophotometer thermostated at 298 K.

References

1. B. PULLMAN and A. PULLMAN, "Quantum Biochemistry", Interscience, New York, 1963, Chap. XI.
2. R. FOSTER, "Organic Charge-Transfer Complexes", Academic, New York, 1969.
3. R. FOSTER in "Molecular Complexes", ed. R. FOSTER, Elek Science, London, 1974, Vol. 2, Chap 3.
4. B. B. BHOWMIK and A. BHATTACHARYYA, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1986, **42**, 1217, 1361; 1988, **44**, 1147.
5. C. REICHARDT in "Molecular Interactions", eds. H. RATAJEZAK and W. J. ORVILLE-THOMAS, Wiley-Interscience, Chichester, 1982, Vol. 3, Chap. 5.
6. P. SYKES, "A Guide Book to Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", 6th. ed., Orient Longman, New Delhi, 1988, Chap. 13.
7. J. MALACKI in "Molecular Interactions", eds. H. RATAJEZAK and W. J. ORVILLE-THOMAS, Wiley-Interscience, 1982, Vol. 3, p. 4.
8. L. P. HAMMETT, "Physical Organic Chemistry", 2nd. ed., New York, 1970.
9. I. L. FINAR, "Organic Chemistry", 6th. ed., ELBS, 1973, pp. 604.
10. S. K. MAITY and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1980, **261**, 573; A. K. MANDAL and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 495; S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 698; M. J. S. DEWAR and P. J. GRISDALE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 3539.

